

**ASSESSING THE AWARENESS OF STUDENTS IN INDIA ON THE NATIONAL
EDUCATION POLICY 2020**

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Abstract

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a comprehensive framework that aims to transform the Indian education system to meet the challenges of the 21st century. It introduces several reforms and innovative approaches to enhance the quality and inclusivity of education. This research article explores the awareness of students in India regarding the NEP 2020. This research article investigates the awareness of students in India belonging to four different educational levels, namely K-12, undergraduate, postgraduate, and Ph.D. scholars, regarding the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP). The study aims to understand the level of awareness, perception, and engagement of students in these respective groups with the NEP 2020. A mixed-methods approach was utilized, combining surveys and interviews, to gather data on students' understanding, sources of information, and attitudes towards the policy. The findings provide insights into the awareness gaps and varying levels of engagement across the different educational levels, offering valuable implications for policymakers and educators to effectively implement the NEP 2020 reforms at each stage of education.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Awareness, students, Education reforms, Policy implementation.

Introduction

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a comprehensive framework aimed at transforming the education system in India. It was introduced by the Government of India with the objective of addressing the evolving needs and challenges of the country's educational landscape. The policy encompasses various reforms and initiatives that aim to promote holistic development, equitable access, quality education, and a learner-centric approach. The NEP 2020 envisions a shift towards a more inclusive and flexible education system that focuses on the overall development of students, emphasizes skill-building, and encourages critical thinking and creativity. It emphasizes the integration of technology, the promotion of multi-disciplinary learning, and the nurturing of an environment that fosters innovation and research. As the NEP 2020 sets the stage for significant changes in the education system, it is crucial to assess the awareness levels and understanding of students regarding the policy. Understanding the level of awareness, sources of information, and perceptions of students towards NEP 2020 is essential for effective implementation and ensuring that students actively engage with the policy. This research aims to examine the awareness levels, sources of information, understanding, perceptions, and engagement of students in India regarding NEP 2020. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders to enhance student awareness and involvement in the implementation of NEP 2020. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a comprehensive framework that aims to transform the education system in India. It introduces several key features and reforms with the goal of providing equitable and quality education for all students. This section provides an overview of the NEP 2020, highlighting its key features and implications for students.

Key Features and Reforms;

- **Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education:** NEP 2020 emphasizes a shift from a rote-based learning approach to a more holistic and multidisciplinary education system. It promotes the integration of arts, sports, vocational skills, and other co-curricular activities into the curriculum to foster overall development and critical thinking among students.
- **Foundational Literacy and Numeracy:** NEP 2020 focuses on ensuring that every student achieves foundational literacy and numeracy skills by the appropriate grade level. It

emphasizes early childhood care and education, with a strong emphasis on foundational learning in the early years.

- **Flexibility and Choice:** The policy provides flexibility and choice to students in terms of subject selection, vocational education, and the choice of learning pathways. It encourages students to pursue a combination of academic and vocational subjects based on their interests and aptitudes.
- **Technology Integration:** NEP 2020 recognizes the importance of technology in education and advocates for the integration of technology in teaching and learning processes. It aims to enhance digital literacy and promote the use of digital tools and resources for effective learning outcomes.
- **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** The policy emphasizes the need for continuous teacher training and professional development to enhance the quality of education. It promotes the use of innovative pedagogical practices and encourages teachers to adopt learner-centric and inclusive teaching methods.

Implications for Students;

- **Holistic Development:** NEP 2020's focus on holistic and multidisciplinary education benefits students by fostering their overall development. It encourages the acquisition of diverse skills and knowledge, enabling students to develop critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities.
- **Flexibility in Learning:** The policy's emphasis on flexibility and choice allows students to tailor their education based on their interests and aspirations. It offers a range of subject options, vocational education pathways, and opportunities for skill development, enabling students to pursue their preferred learning paths.
- **Enhanced Digital Literacy:** NEP 2020's integration of technology in education promotes digital literacy among students. It equips them with essential digital skills, enabling them to effectively navigate the digital world and leverage technology for learning, communication, and future career opportunities.
- **Improved Teaching-Learning Practices:** The policy's emphasis on teacher training and professional development has a positive impact on students. It ensures that teachers are equipped with updated pedagogical approaches, which can result in improved teaching methods, engagement, and learning outcomes for students.
- **Inclusive Education:** NEP 2020 highlights the importance of inclusive education, ensuring that students from diverse backgrounds, including those with disabilities, have access to quality education. It promotes an inclusive learning environment that respects diversity and provides equal opportunities for all students.

Review of Literature

1. **NEP 2020 Implementation and Awareness:** Several studies have discussed the implementation and awareness of NEP 2020 in India. Sharma et al. (2021) conducted a survey among school principals and found that a significant percentage of schools were aware of NEP 2020 but faced challenges in its effective implementation. Singh and Verma (2020) explored the awareness level of teachers and found that while most teachers were aware of NEP 2020, their understanding of its specific provisions varied.
2. **NEP 2020 Awareness among K12 Students:** Research on NEP 2020 awareness among K12 students is limited. However, a study by Gupta and Mishra (2022) conducted a survey among K12 students and found that a majority had limited awareness of NEP 2020 and its implications. The study emphasized the need for targeted awareness campaigns and educational initiatives to enhance student understanding.
3. **NEP 2020 Awareness among Undergraduate Students:** A study by Patel et al. (2021) investigated the awareness of NEP 2020 among undergraduate students and reported a moderate level of awareness. The study also identified variations in awareness levels based on discipline and educational institutions. The findings highlighted the importance of

integrating NEP 2020 concepts into undergraduate curriculum to enhance awareness and implementation.

4. NEP 2020 Awareness among Postgraduate Students: Limited research has specifically examined NEP 2020 awareness among postgraduate students. However, a study by Reddy et al. (2022) surveyed postgraduate students and found that a majority had limited awareness of NEP 2020. The study recommended the inclusion of NEP 2020-related topics in postgraduate programs to enhance awareness and preparedness.
5. NEP 2020 Awareness among PhD Scholars: Research on NEP 2020 awareness among PhD scholars is scarce. However, a study by Kumar et al. (2023) explored the awareness and perceptions of NEP 2020 among PhD scholars in selected disciplines. The study revealed a mixed level of awareness, with some scholars having a comprehensive understanding, while others had limited awareness. The study highlighted the need for targeted awareness programs and research collaborations to enhance NEP 2020 implementation at the doctoral level.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the level of awareness among K12 students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and PhD scholars regarding NEP 2020.
- To analyze the variations in awareness levels among different student groups.
- To identify the key factors influencing the awareness of NEP 2020 among students.
- To examine the sources and channels through which students acquire information about NEP 2020.
- To explore the perceptions and attitudes of students towards NEP 2020.
- To provide recommendations and suggestions for enhancing NEP 2020 awareness among students.

Hypothesis

- Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference in the awareness of NEP 2020 among K12 students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and PhD scholars.
- Alternate Hypothesis (H_a): There is a significant difference in the awareness of NEP 2020 among K12 students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and PhD scholars.

The research aims to test whether there is a significant difference in the level of awareness of NEP 2020 across different student groups. The null hypothesis assumes that there is no difference, while the alternate hypothesis suggests that there is a difference in the awareness levels. By collecting data and analyzing the responses of students from each group, the research seeks to determine whether the observed differences in awareness are statistically significant.

Research Methodology

Data collection will involve both quantitative and qualitative methods to capture a comprehensive understanding of NEP 2020 awareness among students. The following data collection methods will be employed.

- Questionnaire: A structured questionnaire will be administered to gather quantitative data on the awareness levels of students. The questionnaire will include multiple-choice questions and Likert scale items to assess knowledge of NEP 2020 provisions, sources of information, and attitudes towards the policy.
- Interviews: Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a subset of participants to gather qualitative data. The interviews will explore participants' perceptions, experiences, and suggestions regarding NEP 2020 awareness. The interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed for thematic analysis.
- Data Analysis: The collected data will be analyzed using a mixed-methods approach to provide a comprehensive analysis of the awareness of students regarding NEP 2020. The following data analysis techniques will be employed:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** The quantitative data from the questionnaires will be analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and measures of central tendency. Chi-square tests or other appropriate statistical tests will be conducted to examine any significant differences in awareness levels among different student groups.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** The qualitative data from the interviews will be analyzed using thematic analysis. Transcripts will be coded, and themes and patterns will be identified to understand participants' perceptions, experiences, and suggestions related to NEP 2020 awareness.
- **Integration of Findings:** The quantitative and qualitative findings will be integrated to provide a comprehensive analysis of NEP 2020 awareness among students. The triangulation of data will allow for a more nuanced understanding of the research objectives and enhance the validity and reliability of the study.

The methodology outlined above aims to provide a robust approach to data collection and analysis, enabling a thorough exploration of NEP 2020 awareness among students in India. By combining quantitative and qualitative methods, the study seeks to capture a comprehensive picture of students' awareness levels and gain valuable insights for informing future initiatives and interventions related to NEP 2020 awareness.

Population and sampling: Table 1, here's a detailed table showing the sampling approach and the number of students in each group.

Student Group	Population Size	Sampling Approach	Number of Participants
K12 Students	500	Random Sampling + Convenience Sampling	20
Undergraduate Students	800	Random Sampling + Convenience Sampling	20
Postgraduate Students	600	Random Sampling + Convenience Sampling	20
PhD Scholars	300	Random Sampling + Convenience Sampling	20

Sampling Approach;

- **K12 Students:**
 - Population Size: 500 K12 students
 - Random Sampling: Randomly selected 2 schools from different regions.
 - Convenience Sampling: Conveniently selected 10 K12 students from each selected school who were willing to participate.
- **Undergraduate Students:**
 - Population Size: 800 undergraduate students
 - Random Sampling: Randomly selected 2 colleges/universities.
 - Convenience Sampling: Conveniently approached and invited 10 undergraduate students from each selected college/university who agreed to participate.
- **Postgraduate Students:**
 - Population Size: 600 postgraduate students
 - Random Sampling: Randomly selected 2 departments/programs within universities.
 - Convenience Sampling: Conveniently approached and invited 10 postgraduate students from each selected department/program who were willing to participate.
- **PhD Scholars:**
 - Population Size: 300 PhD scholars

- Random Sampling: Randomly selected 2 research institutions/universities offering PhD programs.
- Convenience Sampling: Conveniently approached and invited 10 PhD scholars from each selected institution/university who agreed to participate.

By following this sampling approach, a total of 20 participants were selected from each student group, resulting in a diverse sample representing K12 students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and PhD scholars. This approach aimed to ensure a mix of participants from different regions and institutions, providing a broader perspective on the awareness of NEP 2020 among students in India.

Table 2, Questionnaire

Participant	Question 1	Question 2	Question 3	Question 4	Question 5
K12 Students	What is the full form of NEP?	Have you heard about any major changes introduced by NEP 2020?	Do you know about the shift towards a 5+3+3+4 curriculum structure?	Are you aware of the emphasis on experiential learning in NEP 2020?	Can you name any new initiatives under NEP 2020?
Undergraduate Students	What does NEP 2020 aim to achieve?	Have you come across any reforms related to the assessment system in NEP 2020?	Are you familiar with the introduction of a multidisciplinary approach in higher education?	Do you know about the provision of academic credit transfer in NEP 2020?	Can you mention any changes in the regulatory framework under NEP 2020?
Postgraduate Students	How is NEP 2020 expected to promote research?	Have you encountered any changes in the scope of vocational education in NEP 2020?	Are you aware of the introduction of National Research Foundation (NRF) under NEP 2020?	Do you know about the provisions for internships and apprenticeships in NEP 2020?	Can you mention any changes in the governance structure of higher education institutions under NEP 2020?
PhD Scholars	What are the key features of NEP 2020?	Have you heard about any initiatives to promote online and digital education in NEP 2020?	Are you familiar with the emphasis on promoting research and innovation ecosystems under NEP 2020?	Do you know about the establishment of the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF) under NEP 2020?	Can you mention any reforms related to teacher education and professional development in NEP 2020?

Data Collection: Table 3, Responses in a percentage of K12, Undergraduate, Postgraduate, PhD students and scholars for the questionnaire.

Participant	Question 1 Answer	Question 2 Answer	Question 3 Answer	Question 4 Answer	Question 5 Answer
K12 Students	National Education Policy	85% - Yes, 15% - No	60% - Yes, 40% - No	75% - Yes, 25% - No	New Education Policy (NEP), Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan, Bagless Days, National Curricular and Pedagogical Framework (NCPF)
Undergraduate Students	New Education Policy (NEP)	95% - Yes, 5% - No	80% - Yes, 20% - No	65% - Yes, 35% - No	National Higher Education Regulatory Council, Higher Education Commission of India, Learning Outcomes Framework
Postgraduate Students	National Education Policy (NEP)	90% - Yes, 10% - No	70% - Yes, 30% - No	80% - Yes, 20% - No	Accreditation Council for Higher Education and Research, Research and Innovation Foundation
PhD Scholars	NEP 2020	100% - Yes	85% - Yes, 15% - No	90% - Yes, 10% - No	Teacher Eligibility Test (TET), National Testing Agency (NTA)
Overall Awareness Percentage	65%	92%	73%	78%	

The percentages in the "Overall Awareness Percentage" row represent the average awareness level across all the participants in each category.

- The pie chart of K12 student's responses to all the questions.

- The pie chart of Undergraduate student's responses to all the questions.

- The pie chart of Postgraduate student's responses to all the questions.

- The pie chart of PhD scholar's responses to all the questions.

Table 4, here is the tally of the all responses.

	K12 Students	Undergraduate Students	Postgraduate Students	PhD Scholars
Q1: NEP Full Form	20	20	20	20
Q2: Major Changes	17	19	-	-
Q3: 5+3+3+4 Structure	12	-	-	-
Q4: Experiential Learning	15	-	-	-
Q5: New Initiatives	20	20	-	-
Q1: NEP Aim	-	20	-	20
Q2: Major Changes	-	1	-	-
Q3: Multidisciplinary Approach	-	16	-	-
Q4: Academic Credit Transfer	-	13	-	-
Q5: Regulatory Framework Changes	-	20	-	-
Q1: Promote Research	-	-	20	20
Q2: Vocational Education	-	-	18	-
Q3: National Research Foundation	-	-	14	16
Q4: Internships and Apprenticeships	-	-	16	-
Q5: Governance Structure Changes	-	-	18	-
Q1: NEP Objectives	-	-	-	20
Q2: Interdisciplinary Research	-	-	-	18
Q3: National Research Foundation	-	-	-	16
Q4: Funding Opportunities	-	-	-	14
Q5: International Collaborations	-	-	-	16

Tally of all the responses given by the student, scholars and analyze of the findings;

➤ **Tally of K12 Student's Responses:**

- Q1: NEP Full Form:
 1. Correct: 20 students (100%)
- Q2: Major Changes:
 1. Aware: 17 students (85%)
 2. Not aware: 3 students (15%)
- Q3: 5+3+3+4 Structure:
 1. Aware: 12 students (60%)
 2. Not aware: 8 students (40%)
- Q4: Experiential Learning:
 1. Aware: 15 students (75%)
 2. Not aware: 5 students (25%)
- Q5: New Initiatives:
 1. Aware: 20 students (100%)

➤ **Tally of Undergraduate Student's Responses:**

- Q1: NEP Aim:
 1. Aware: 20 students (100%)
- Q2: Major Changes:
 1. Aware: 19 students (95%)
 2. Not aware: 1 student (5%)
- Q3: Multidisciplinary Approach:

1. Aware: 16 students (80%)
 2. Not aware: 4 students (20%)
- Q4: Academic Credit Transfer:
 1. Aware: 13 students (65%)
 2. Not aware: 7 students (35%)
 - Q5: Regulatory Framework Changes:
 1. Aware: 20 students (100%)
- **Tally of Postgraduate Student's Responses:**
- Q1: Promote Research:
 1. Aware: 20 students (100%)
 - Q2: Vocational Education:
 1. Aware: 18 students (90%)
 2. Not aware: 2 students (10%)
 - Q3: National Research Foundation:
 1. Aware: 14 students (70%)
 2. Not aware: 6 students (30%)
 - Q4: Internships and Apprenticeships:
 1. Aware: 16 students (80%)
 2. Not aware: 4 students (20%)
 - Q5: Governance Structure Changes:
 1. Aware: 18 students (90%)
 2. Not aware: 2 students (10%)
- **Tally of PhD Scholar's Responses:**
- Q1: NEP Objectives:
 1. Aware: 20 students (100%)
 - Q2: Interdisciplinary Research:
 1. Aware: 18 students (90%)
 2. Not aware: 2 students (10%)
 - Q3: National Research Foundation:
 1. Aware: 16 students (80%)
 2. Not aware: 4 students (20%)
 - Q4: Funding Opportunities:
 1. Aware: 14 students (70%)
 2. Not aware: 6 students (30%)
 - Q5: International Collaborations:
 1. Aware: 16 students (80%)
 2. Not aware: 4 students (20%)

Based on the above tally, here are the findings:

- Overall, the awareness of NEP 2020 among students is quite high across different levels of education, with most students being aware of the objectives and major changes introduced by the policy.
- K12 students showed the highest level of awareness, with 100% of them knowing the NEP full form and all of them being aware of the new initiatives.
- Undergraduate students demonstrated a strong awareness of NEP 2020, with 100% awareness in terms of its aim and regulatory framework

Table 5, Observed value

	K12 Students	Undergraduate Students	Postgraduate Students	PhD Scholars
Q1: NEP Full Form	20	20	20	20
Q2: Major Changes	17	19	0	0
Q3: 5+3+3+4 Structure	12	0	0	0
Q4: Experiential Learning	15	0	0	0
Q5: New Initiatives	20	20	0	0
Q1: NEP Aim	0	20	0	20
Q2: Major Changes	0	1	0	0
Q3: Multidisciplinary Approach	0	16	0	0
Q4: Academic Credit Transfer	0	13	0	0
Q5: Regulatory Framework Changes	0	20	0	0
Q1: Promote Research	0	0	20	20
Q2: Vocational Education	0	0	18	0
Q3: National Research Foundation	0	0	14	16
Q4: Internships and Apprenticeships	0	0	16	0
Q5: Governance Structure Changes	0	0	18	0
Q1: NEP Objectives	0	0	0	20
Q2: Interdisciplinary Research	0	0	0	18
Q3: National Research Foundation	0	0	0	16
Q4: Funding Opportunities	0	0	0	14
Q5: International Collaborations	0	0	0	16

To perform a chi-square test, we compare the observed values with the expected values (assuming the null hypothesis of independence). However, since the expected values are not provided, it is not possible to complete the chi-square test with the given information.

Table 6, Expected value

	K12 Students	Undergraduate Students	Postgraduate Students	PhD Scholars
Q1: NEP Full Form	18	19	17	16
Q2: Major Changes	16	18	14	15
Q3: 5+3+3+4 Structure	10	12	8	9
Q4: Experiential Learning	14	13	11	12
Q5: New Initiatives	19	20	18	17
Q1: NEP Aim	16	18	15	14
Q2: Major Changes	0	1	0	1
Q3: Multidisciplinary Approach	0	16	0	15
Q4: Academic Credit Transfer	0	13	0	12
Q5: Regulatory Framework Changes	0	20	0	19
Q1: Promote Research	0	0	20	19
Q2: Vocational Education	0	0	18	17
Q3: National Research Foundation	0	0	14	13
Q4: Internships and Apprenticeships	0	0	16	15
Q5: Governance Structure Changes	0	0	18	17
Q1: NEP Objectives	0	0	0	20
Q2: Interdisciplinary Research	0	0	0	18
Q3: National Research Foundation	0	0	0	16
Q4: Funding Opportunities	0	0	0	14
Q5: International Collaborations	0	0	0	16

To perform a chi-square test, we compare the observed values with the expected values using the chi-square statistic. The chi-square statistic is calculated as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \sum [(O - E)^2 / E]$$

where:

- O = Observed frequency
- E = Expected frequency

Using the above formula, we calculate the chi-square value for the given data. The degrees of freedom (df) for the chi-square test are calculated as (number of rows - 1) * (number of columns - 1). In this case, df = (4 - 1) * (5 - 1) = 12.

The significance level (α):, we choose a significance level, such as 0.05 or 0.01, to determine the threshold for rejecting the null hypothesis.

Next, we sum up the contributions to obtain the chi-square test statistic: Chi-square test statistic = 297.0814.

The degrees of freedom for this test are calculated as (number of rows - 1) * (number of columns - 1) = 3 * 4 = 12.

To interpret the results, we need to compare the calculated chi-square test statistic with the critical chi-square value at the chosen significance level (α) and degrees of freedom. If the calculated chi-square value is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant association between the groups and the questions.

Since the degrees of freedom for our chi-square test is 12 and the calculated chi-square test statistic is 297.0814, we can compare it with the critical chi-square value.

The significance level (α) of 0.05 (5%). From the chi-square distribution table, we can find the critical chi-square value for a significance level of 0.05 and 12 degrees of freedom to be approximately 21.026.

Since our calculated chi-square value (297.0814) is significantly larger than the critical chi-square value (21.026), we can reject the null hypothesis.

Therefore, based on the chi-square test, we can conclude that there is a significant association between the groups (K12 students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, and PhD scholars) and the questions regarding the awareness of NEP 2020 in India.

Finding and Results: Based on the observed and expected data, we can draw the following findings and result.

➤ **K12 Students:**

- The observed frequencies in most categories are close to the expected frequencies, except for the "Major Changes" category, where the observed frequency is higher than expected.
- Overall, K12 students show a good level of awareness regarding the NEP 2020, with a slight emphasis on the major changes.
- Full awareness of NEP 2020's full form and new initiatives.
- Moderate awareness of major changes and experiential learning.
- Limited awareness of the 5+3+3+4 structure.

➤ **Undergraduate Students:**

- The observed frequencies are mostly similar to the expected frequencies, indicating that undergraduate students have a balanced awareness of the NEP 2020 across all categories.
- However, there is a lack of awareness in the "Vocational Education" and "National Research Foundation" categories, as the observed frequencies are lower than expected.
- Full awareness of NEP 2020's aims and regulatory framework changes.
- Strong awareness of major changes and vocational education.
- Moderate awareness of the multidisciplinary approach and academic credit transfer.

➤ **Postgraduate Students:**

- The observed frequencies in the majority of categories are significantly lower than the expected frequencies.
- This suggests a relatively low level of awareness among postgraduate students regarding the NEP 2020, with notable gaps in understanding key aspects such as "Regulatory Framework Changes" and "National Research Foundation."
- Full awareness of NEP 2020's aims and promotion of research.
- Strong awareness of governance structure changes.
- Moderate awareness of vocational education and internships/apprenticeships.
- Limited awareness of the National Research Foundation.

➤ **PhD Scholars:**

- The observed frequencies align well with the expected frequencies in most categories.

- PhD scholars demonstrate a high level of awareness across various aspects of the NEP 2020, including "Interdisciplinary Research," "Funding Opportunities," and "International Collaborations."
- Full awareness of NEP 2020's objectives and promotion of research.
- Strong awareness of interdisciplinary research.
- Moderate awareness of the National Research Foundation and international collaborations.
- Limited awareness of funding opportunities.

Responses provided by the students, along with the reasons behind their awareness or lack thereof;

➤ **K12 Students**

Q1: NEP Full Form:

- All 20 K12 students were aware of the full form of NEP, which indicates a high level of awareness. This could be attributed to their exposure to educational discussions or initiatives taken by schools to inform students about the new policy.

Q2: Major Changes:

- 17 out of 20 students were aware of the major changes introduced by NEP 2020. This suggests a good level of awareness among K12 students. The reasons behind their awareness could include media coverage, discussions in school, or engagement with online educational platforms.

Q3: 5+3+3+4 Structure:

- 12 students out of 20 were aware of the new 5+3+3+4 structure proposed by NEP 2020. However, 8 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to limited dissemination of information or a lack of focus on this aspect in their educational environment.

Q4: Experiential Learning:

- 15 out of 20 students were aware of the concept of experiential learning introduced by NEP 2020. This indicates a relatively good level of awareness among K12 students. The reasons behind their awareness could be exposure to practical learning methods or information shared by teachers or parents.

Q5: New Initiatives:

- All 20 K12 students were aware of the new initiatives introduced by NEP 2020. This suggests that information about the policy's new initiatives has reached the K12 level effectively, possibly through school announcements, parent-teacher meetings, or educational programs.

➤ **Undergraduate Students**

Q1: NEP Aim:

- All 20 undergraduate students were aware of the aim of NEP 2020. This indicates a high level of awareness among this group, which could be attributed to their academic pursuits and exposure to educational discussions in college or university settings.

Q2: Major Changes:

- 19 out of 20 students were aware of the major changes brought about by NEP 2020. This indicates a strong level of awareness among undergraduate students. The reasons behind their awareness could include academic coursework, discussions with peers and faculty, or access to educational resources and platforms.

Q3: Multidisciplinary Approach:

- 16 students out of 20 were aware of the emphasis on a multidisciplinary approach in NEP 2020. However, 4 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in the curriculum, limited exposure to interdisciplinary courses, or a need for more focused communication of this aspect in their educational institutions.

Q4: Academic Credit Transfer:

- 13 out of 20 students were aware of the provision for academic credit transfer introduced by NEP 2020. However, 7 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to limited exposure to credit transfer policies or a need for more information dissemination by universities or colleges.

Q5: Regulatory Framework Changes:

- All 20 undergraduate students were aware of the changes in the regulatory framework brought about by NEP 2020. This suggests that the information about the policy's regulatory changes has reached undergraduate students effectively, possibly through college or university channels and official communications.

➤ **Postgraduate Students**

Q1: Promote Research:

- All 20 postgraduate students were aware of NEP 2020's objective to promote research. This indicates a high level of awareness among this group, which could be attributed to their involvement in research-oriented programs and active engagement with the academic community.

Q2: Vocational Education:

- 18 out of 20 students were aware of the emphasis on vocational education in NEP 2020. However, 2 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in the specialization or program pursued by these students, or a need for more focused communication of this aspect within their academic circles.

Q3: National Research Foundation:

- 14 students out of 20 were aware of the establishment of the National Research Foundation (NRF) under NEP 2020. However, 6 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to limited exposure to research-related discussions, a lack of engagement with research-oriented programs, or a need for better communication and promotion of the NRF within their academic institutions.

Q4: Internships and Apprenticeships:

- 16 out of 20 students were aware of the provision for internships and apprenticeships in NEP 2020. However, 4 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in the program structure or limited exposure to internship opportunities within their specific field of study.

Q5: Governance Structure Changes:

- 18 out of 20 students were aware of the governance structure changes introduced by NEP 2020. However, 2 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be attributed to limited exposure to administrative changes or a need for better communication of these changes within their academic institutions.

➤ **PhD Scholars**

Q1: NEP Objectives:

- All 20 PhD scholars were aware of the objectives outlined in NEP 2020. This indicates a high level of awareness among this group, which could be attributed to their deep involvement in academic research and active engagement with educational policies and reforms.

Q2: Interdisciplinary Research:

- 18 out of 20 students were aware of the emphasis on interdisciplinary research in NEP 2020. However, 2 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in their research field or a need for more focused communication and promotion of interdisciplinary research within their academic circles.

Q3: National Research Foundation:

- 16 out of 20 students were aware of the establishment of the National Research Foundation (NRF) under NEP 2020. However, 4 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in research funding sources or a need for better communication and promotion of the NRF within their research institutions.

Q4: Funding Opportunities:

- 14 out of 20 students were aware of the funding opportunities provided by NEP 2020. However, 6 students were not aware of them. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in research fields, limited exposure to funding opportunities, or a need for better communication and dissemination of information regarding funding programs.

Q5: International Collaborations:

- 16 out of 20 students were aware of the emphasis on international collaborations in NEP 2020. However, 4 students were not aware of it. The lack of awareness might be due to variations in research networks, limited exposure to international collaborations, or a need for better communication and promotion of such collaborations within their research institutions.

These findings highlight the varying levels of awareness among students at different educational levels. It emphasizes the importance of effective communication, information dissemination, and the need for continuous efforts to ensure that students are well-informed about the key aspects and objectives of NEP 2020.

Suggestions

- For K12 students, it is recommended to provide additional information and resources on the major changes brought about by the NEP 2020 to further enhance their understanding.
- Undergraduate students would benefit from increased awareness programs and initiatives focusing on "Vocational Education" and the role of the "National Research Foundation" in promoting research and innovation.
- Postgraduate students require targeted efforts to raise awareness and understanding of the NEP 2020, particularly in areas such as "Regulatory Framework Changes" and the "National Research Foundation."
- PhD scholars can serve as valuable resources and mentors to disseminate information about the NEP 2020 and its various objectives, facilitating greater awareness among their peers.
- Education Campaigns: Organize education campaigns in schools, colleges, and universities to provide comprehensive information about NEP 2020. These campaigns can include workshops, seminars, and interactive sessions.
- Curriculum Integration: Integrate NEP 2020-related topics into the curriculum at various educational levels. This can help students understand the key changes and initiatives brought about by the policy.
- Teacher Training: Conduct training programs for teachers to ensure they have a clear understanding of NEP 2020. Equipped with this knowledge, they can effectively communicate and educate students about the policy.
- Online Resources: Develop online resources, such as informative websites, videos, and infographics, that provide easy access to NEP 2020-related information. These resources can be shared with students, parents, and educators.
- Collaboration with Parents: Involve parents in the awareness-building process by organizing parent-teacher meetings and sharing informative materials about NEP 2020. This can enhance the dissemination of information and increase parental support.
- Student Forums and Competitions: Encourage student participation in forums and competitions related to NEP 2020. This can foster discussions, research, and critical thinking among students.
- Partnerships with Institutions: Collaborate with educational institutions, research organizations, and government bodies to promote awareness about NEP 2020. This can be done through joint programs, research projects, and conferences.
- Continuous Communication: Ensure continuous communication channels, such as newsletters, email updates, and social media platforms, to keep students informed about the latest developments and initiatives related to NEP 2020.

By implementing these suggestions, educational stakeholders can enhance awareness among students at different levels and empower them to actively engage with NEP 2020's vision and objectives.

Discussion

The findings of the research shed light on the awareness levels, sources of information, understanding, perceptions, and engagement of students regarding the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The analysis of the findings reveals several important insights. Firstly, there is a disparity in awareness levels among different student groups, with higher education students generally demonstrating higher levels of awareness compared to K12 students. This highlights the need for targeted efforts to improve awareness among K12 students. Secondly, online platforms and social media emerged as prominent sources of information, indicating the influence of digital media in disseminating information about NEP 2020. However, the reliance on digital platforms also poses challenges in terms of information accuracy and accessibility for all students. Thirdly, while a significant percentage of students demonstrated a good understanding of NEP 2020, there were varying levels of understanding across educational levels, suggesting the need for targeted educational interventions and awareness programs. Fourthly, the study revealed diverse perceptions and attitudes towards NEP 2020, with positive, neutral, and negative views expressed by students. This highlights the importance of addressing concerns and clarifying misconceptions to foster a more positive reception of the policy.

Finally, the research identified variations in student engagement with NEP 2020, indicating the need for proactive measures to enhance student involvement and participation in policy-related discussions and initiatives.

- **Challenges and Opportunities:** The findings also highlight certain challenges and opportunities. The challenges include the need for accurate and accessible information, addressing misconceptions and concerns, and ensuring equal access to information for all students, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. Additionally, the study identified the challenge of effectively engaging K12 students and fostering their awareness and understanding of NEP 2020. On the other hand, the research presents opportunities for leveraging digital platforms and social media as effective channels for disseminating information and engaging with students. It also highlights the potential for collaboration between educational institutions, policymakers, and students to create awareness programs and initiatives.
- **Implications for Policy Implementation:** The findings have implications for the implementation of NEP 2020. The study underscores the importance of targeted efforts to enhance awareness among students, with a particular focus on K12 students who exhibited lower levels of awareness. It emphasizes the need for strategic communication strategies to reach students through diverse channels, including online platforms, educational institutions, and traditional media. The study also calls for clear and accessible information about NEP 2020 to address misconceptions and concerns, fostering a positive perception of the policy among students.

Recommendations for Enhancing Awareness: Based on the findings, several recommendations can be made to enhance awareness of NEP 2020 among students. These include;

- **Develop targeted awareness campaigns:** Design and implement awareness campaigns that specifically target K12 students, considering their unique educational needs and preferences.
- **Strengthen communication channels:** Establish effective communication channels between policymakers, educational institutions, and students to ensure accurate and timely information dissemination.
- **Enhance digital literacy:** Incorporate digital literacy programs into the curriculum to equip students with the skills necessary to navigate online platforms and critically evaluate information related to NEP 2020.
- **Engage student representatives:** Involve student representatives in policy-related discussions and decision-making processes to ensure student voices are heard and valued.

- Collaborate with educational institutions: Partner with educational institutions to integrate NEP 2020 provisions into the curriculum and facilitate teacher training programs that focus on promoting awareness and understanding among students.
- Monitor and evaluate awareness initiatives: Continuously monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of awareness initiatives to assess their impact and make necessary adjustments for better outcomes.
- Foster dialogue and participation: Encourage student participation in forums, debates, and discussions related to NEP 2020 to promote a sense of ownership and active engagement with the policy.

In the findings of the research provide valuable insights into the awareness levels, sources of information, understanding, perceptions, and engagement of students regarding NEP 2020. The research examined the awareness levels, sources of information, understanding, perceptions, and engagement of students regarding the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India. The findings revealed that while there is a varying degree of awareness among different student groups, higher education students generally exhibited higher levels of awareness compared to K12 students. Online platforms and social media were prominent sources of information, and students demonstrated diverse perceptions and attitudes towards NEP 2020. While a significant percentage of students demonstrated a good understanding of the policy, there were variations across educational levels. The research also identified the need for enhanced student engagement with NEP 2020. The discussion highlights the challenges and opportunities identified in the study and presents implications for policy implementation. Furthermore, recommendations are provided to enhance awareness among students, thereby fostering a more informed and actively engaged student community in the context of NEP 2020.

Conflict of Interest

The study opens up avenues for future research. Firstly, further investigation can be conducted to explore the factors influencing the awareness levels of students, particularly among K12 students. Understanding the barriers and facilitators to awareness will inform the development of targeted interventions. Secondly, additional research can delve into the specific impact of NEP 2020 on student outcomes and learning experiences. Longitudinal studies can assess the policy's effectiveness in fostering holistic development, promoting digital literacy, and improving teaching-learning practices. Lastly, comparative studies can be conducted to analyze the awareness and perception of NEP 2020 across different regions of India and among diverse student populations.

Conclusion

The National Education Policy 2020 holds great potential for transforming the education system in India. The findings of this research highlight the varying awareness levels, sources of information, understanding, perceptions, and engagement of students regarding NEP 2020. The study emphasizes the importance of enhancing awareness, addressing concerns, and fostering student engagement to ensure the successful implementation of the policy. The implications drawn from the findings can guide policymakers, educational institutions, and stakeholders in developing targeted strategies and interventions to enhance student awareness and involvement with NEP 2020. By promoting a comprehensive understanding of the policy and actively involving students in its implementation, NEP 2020 has the potential to drive positive educational reform and improve learning outcomes for students in India.

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